

VERBS OF VISUAL PERCEPTION FROM A LINGUISTIC POINT OF VIEW

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Abstract. *The functioning of the personality is conditioned by a number of numerous factors that are often an immanent component of human existence. Without being aware of these factors at first glance, upon their purposeful consideration, we are aware that life without them would be unthinkable. Among these special components, without any doubt, belong sensory systems, and among them - the most significant for us - visual. The phenomenon of visual perception appears in the studies of representatives of various scientific fields.*

Vision, not without reason, is a mystery that has troubled human thought from time immemorial. This sensory system is considered the most well studied of all other sensory systems. It is characterized by great significance, its functionality forms a wide range of vital factors. So, for numerous species of the animal world, vision is a source of critically important knowledge about objects and events in the environment. This knowledge is conditioned by information such as color and movement, shape and texture, size and distance, luminance and brightness, as well as information about how these distinguishing features of the environment affect each other.

Keywords: *vision, visual perception, verbs of visual perception, sensory systems, visual perceptions.*

Introduction. If, in relation to the animal world, the visual system is predominant for a wide range of species, but not for all (there are such animal species for which, for example, the sense of smell performs a much more important function), then in relation to a person, the priority of vision is observed against the background of other sensory systems. . Scientists have found that half of the cerebral cortex is involved in the processing of visual information.

Materials and methods. It is well known that light is a physical stimulus for the visual system. Light is “radiant energy perceived by the eye and making the surrounding world visible”. Light as a wave phenomenon is characterized by both wavelength and intensity. These physical features of light cause various psychological phenomena. So, the perception of colors and their shades depends on the wavelength. It should be understood that only a small segment of the spectrum of electromagnetic waves is essential for the visual systems of animals and humans. The wavelengths of the electromagnetic spectrum vary over a very wide range. Very short and very long waves are invisible. Most vertebrates, under normal conditions, perceive radiant energy only in the form of wavelengths of approximately 380 nm to 760 nm. This interval is only a seventieth part of the spectrum of electromagnetic waves, but even this small part of the radiant energy, perceived by representatives of the animal and human worlds, guarantees them the right conditions for existence, satisfying the needs, the necessary conditions for survival. The intensity of light, in turn, when interacting with the sensory impression of each individual, forms a subjective effect called brightness.

In order for the energy of light radiation to be informative, it must affect the visual system, i.e. it is transformed into a neural form, which is carried out by the action of radiant energy on light-sensitive tissue. The resulting impulses transmit sensory information.

The main "tool" that guarantees access to visual information is, of course, the eyes. This organ makes it possible to assimilate the maximum of visual information, the volume of which is determined by the requirements of the natural habitat of this species. The anatomy of the eye of all vertebrates is the same. The eye has a photosensitive layer - the retina and the lens, the optical properties of which allow the image to be focused on the retina. The eyeball, which has a spherical shape, is located in the deepening of the skull that protects it. The diameter of the eyeball is approximately 20 mm. Outside, the eyeball is covered with sclera - white (it is this that gives the eye whiteness), an opaque shell about 1 mm thick. On the anterior surface of the eye, the sclera passes into the transparent cornea. The light entering the eye, reflected from surrounding objects, is refracted, and then the refracted rays are focused on the back surface of the eyeball, on the retina. Rays of light entering the eye are refracted to the greatest extent in the cornea. The second eye membrane (about 0.2 mm thick) - vascular - is associated with the sclera, consists mainly of blood vessels and is the main source that feeds the eye. The highly pigmented and dark choroid absorbs excess light that enters the eye, reducing the reflection of light rays inside the eyeball and thereby preventing a fuzzy image.

The most anterior part of the choroid, a stained concentric disk, is called the iris. It is an extremely complex landscape from a biological point of view, filled with rings, dashes, dots, specks, grooves, cobwebs, and the like. The iris of each person has more than 250 distinctive features that are peculiar only to him alone and not inherent in the irises of other people. Since many of the hallmarks of the iris are not only unique but also stable, they can be used in recognition and identification of a person. For such purposes, the iris is much better suited than many other physical features, including the papillary lines on which fingerprinting is based.

We also add that the retina is a complex network of nerve cells and photoreceptors that absorb light energy and transform it into neural activity. The complexity of the structure of the retina in vertebrates reflects its close relationship with one of the most complex and important neural structures - the brain. In the early stages of embryonic development, the retina, brain, and spinal cord are formed from the same tissues. In many ways, the surface of the retina is an extension of the brain. The retina contains two types of photoreceptors: rods and cones. Their outer shell contains a light-absorbing pigment. The optic nerve emerges from the retina and travels to the brain. Despite the complexity of the structure of the visual organ, we confine ourselves to the proposed characteristics - the information provided is sufficient for an introduction to the problem.

In turn, it is important to communicate the meaning of color vision verbs. The phenomenon of color perception is in the center of attention not only of philologists, psychologists, but also artists, poets, philosophers. This fact is not surprising due to the fact that color is inherent in literally all objects of the environment. Color determines the fundamental differences of some surfaces and objects from others, it can be a source of aesthetic and emotional impressions based on general and individual associations. There is no doubt that the color attracts attention, it is able to make a strong impression on someone. Color underlies aesthetic pleasure and, what is very important, is a source of information - with its help we distinguish one object from another, identify many objects, which gives the world around us the

necessary stability. The ability to see color is undoubtedly a biological advantage that gives the world physical integrity.

Results and discussions. Color perception is a subjective result of the impact on the nervous system of a reflected beam belonging to the visible part of the spectrum and having a certain wavelength. So, for example, when people talk about "blue" or "red" light, they mean short- or long-wavelength light, respectively, which, acting on the visual system, causes the sensation of blue or red colors. Colors depend on how the visual system interprets light rays with different wavelengths. Color is not an inherent property of the visible spectrum, but a product of the activity of the visual system; color vision is a psychological phenomenon. In his essay, Rays do not have color W. Wright gives a good definition of the fundamental difference between the physical parameters of light and the psychological phenomenon - color vision: Our sensations of color are inside us, and as long as there is no observer who perceives color, there is no color itself. Even in the chain of events taking place between the receptors of the retina and the visual cortex, there are no colors yet, they appear only when the information receives a final interpretation in the mind of the observer.

In order for a person not to lose orientation in the surrounding world, the constancy of perception comes to the rescue, defined by H. Schiffman as a tendency to perceive the physical properties of objects unchanged despite changes in illumination, distance, and the position of the observer. There are four forms of perceptual constancy: constancy of color perception – it is in the focus of special attention; the essence of the constancy of perception is reduced to the perception of the color of an object as constant, regardless of the wavelength of the light illuminating it. The other three types of perceptual constancy include: lightness constancy (the constancy of the lightness of an object or surface despite changes in its illumination), size constancy (the tendency to perceive the size of objects as relatively constant despite changes in the distance from which they are viewed, and the magnitude of their retinal images) and constancy of form (the tendency to perceive an object as relatively invariant in form, regardless of the position from which it is viewed and the form of its retinal image).

The fundamental problem related to the issue of perception is the correspondence of perception to reality, i.e. how great is the correspondence of the physical world to the subjective world created by our sensations. The concreteness and reality of the external world seem to be undeniable, but perhaps our perception does not quite correspond to reality?

In addressing this problem, it is necessary to cite data from the field of psychology, which focuses, among other things, on understanding the connection between the external environment and conscious human experience. You should focus on concepts such as sensation and perception. These terms denote different phenomena, but it is very difficult to draw a line between them. Thus, sensation is a term denoting the initial processes of detecting and encoding the energy of the physical world. Without going beyond visual perception, it should be said that this energy will be light, to which the retina of the eye reacts, transforming it into a bioelectric neural signal sent to the brain. Perception, in turn, is already the result of psychological processes in which such concepts as meaning, relationships, context, subjective assessment, previous experience of the individual and memory are involved. It follows from this that perception is preceded by sensation, i.e. perception is the result of the ordering of sensations and their transformation into knowledge about the elements of the surrounding world. As we have already mentioned, the boundary between sensation and perception is fuzzy, both phenomena are

closely related, so some scientists propose to adhere to an integrated approach, avoiding a clear distinction between sensation and perception.

As a result of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Despite the complexity of the issue under consideration, the properties of perception have always been in the focus of attention of representatives of different fields of knowledge. Interest in sensation and perception goes back to the beginnings of human intellectual history. Already in ancient Greece, philosophers pondered how a person cognizes the world around him. Aristotle believed that a person owes all knowledge to his own experience acquired through sensations. It was this philosopher who created the basic classification, within which five senses are distinguished - sight, hearing, taste, smell and touch.

Questions that are of interest to linguists studying the verbs of sensation and perception are closely related to the verbs of visual perception. The problems of perception and sensation are historically closely related to the problems of other sciences, therefore, for example, when studying vision, one cannot but take into account the semantic nature of verbs associated with visual perception.

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